

A novel security and vulnerability assessment framework for the protection of public spaces

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Abstract:

The present paper introduces a comprehensive urban security and vulnerability assessment framework that has been developed within the SAFE-CITIES EU-funded project. The proposed framework introduces a coherent methodical approach to characterize the security functions of a public space, including its physical protection and emergency response after major events. Through the facilitation of multi-stakeholders' partnerships and defined protection objectives, the proposed framework has the inherent capability to consider security-by-design of public spaces, drive risk-informed interventions for the protection of public urban spaces and mass events, and support optimal allocation of resources. It is also an inherent approach that allows to tackle different adversarial threats that include CBRN (e.g., RDD, RED) and combined use of emerging technologies such as UAS.

Keywords: Public Spaces; Soft Targets; Urban Security; Urban Target Attractiveness; Risk Assessment; Threat Characterization; Vulnerability Assessment; Security by Design.

Citation: To be added by editorial staff during production.

Academic Editor: Firstname Last-name

Received: date

Revised: date

Accepted: date

Published: date

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1. Introduction

Public spaces within urban environments and mass / public events are by nature an attractive target vulnerable to adversary actions seeking to perform malevolent acts. Persisting terrorist attacks carried out in public spaces highlight the need to strengthen efforts to enhance the protection of public spaces. Rapidly transforming cities and communities are required to search and implement novel concepts and technological solutions for increasing the security of public spaces, ensuring the integrity of physical structures, enhance safety at crowded places and reduce feelings of insecurity. Recent trends that are explored include the introduction of evidence-based urban design, planning and

management measures within proposals for urban development, emphasizing measures to embed protective physical features and encourage prosocial behaviour through the design and management of a location of interest [1,2]. Additionally, the novel “security by design” concept [3] is being used as a measure to increase security and promote public safety through the design of public spaces, lighting and public awareness campaigns as part of urban regeneration measures.

The majority of European public spaces and major events, such as religious / worship places, transportation hubs and stations, public and recreation parks / tourism sites, business areas, educational establishments, major sports and cultural events, mass gatherings etc., which are potentially high-value targets, are exposed to different and diverse threats and each is characterized with unique vulnerabilities. An initial assessment of public spaces modes of attackers revealed a diverse type of attacks that could range from easily attainable low-sophistication weapons to the use of firearms and explosives, and potentially CBRN agents. Recently, the use of unmanned vehicles, mainly aerial but also ground or (under)water ones, is of raising concern as it augments the adversaries’ capabilities.

The rights and characteristics offered by public spaces, rights that must be guaranteed and stimulated by the urban design of places themselves, should ensure that citizens can continue their daily lives while also enjoying safety and security. However, because of this characteristic, all these crowded sites and other ‘soft targets’ are the most vulnerable and prone to risks, which need to be dealt with through protection, prevention and response measures. The challenge lies in the fact that the open and public character of these spaces, which by their nature entail unpredictable actions, make it particularly difficult to adopt measures without altering this nature. These principles are at the core of the place-making approach, which aims to improve the quality of public spaces by involving citizens, supporting health, promoting environmental sustainability and ultimately creating authentic public spaces: an integrated approach that, to be successful, must consider safety as a key factor in urban design, management and programming.

The protection of public spaces requires holistic and integrated approaches, connecting relevant strategies across institutional levels and organizational boundaries, that are based on multi-stakeholder public-private partnerships and citizen engagement processes. The present work, developed through the framework of the Horizon Europe SAFE-CITIES funded project, defines a systematic Security and Vulnerability Assessment (SVA) for public spaces that is based on formal risk management (e.g., ISO31000) and the EU Vulnerability Assessment practices [4], previous and ongoing research results and actions.

Typically, operational vulnerability assessments are carried out by experts with limited participation and collaboration from other stakeholders, and only recently new concepts have been researched. The most notable research projects in the public space protection domain include PRoTECT (<https://protect-cities.eu/>) [5] that provided EU municipalities with an operational perspective based on good practices to access technology concepts, and the knowledge that can be tailored to their needs, Secu4All [6], empowered local and regional authorities with theoretical knowledge and practical tools building on training programs in four areas: vulnerability assessment, crisis communication, innovative technologies & urban planning, whereas STEPWISE [7], proposed innovative tools to bring new capabilities based on rapid creation of Virtual Reality (VR) mock-ups. Technology oriented solutions and smart cities based concepts are also a recent trend introducing data from city-wide lattice of cameras, environmental sensors and multiple interconnected AI systems (IMPETUS [8]), augmenting City Spaces Situation Awareness with intelligence, context and evaluated real-time cyber and physical security threat levels (S4All-Cities [9]), and the simulation of crowds, people with reduced mobility, baggage handling and security inside a complex transportation hub (FAIR Stations [10]). European municipalities have contributed to the development of the research of public space protection and the uptake of innovative solutions noting the PRoTECT [5], PACTESUR [11], BeSecureFeelSecure [12], ToNite [13] building on local community networks and peer to peer exchanges.

The aim of the proposed SVA framework is to provide a uniform methodology that can be followed synergistically by all actors involved in the security of public spaces including both the public and private sectors. The proposed concepts solidify existing experience and knowledge in this challenging area and lays the groundwork for establishing a concrete methodology with the support of modern tools (e.g., digital twins) for stronger cooperation between the public and the private sector, including citizens participation and better anticipation of current and future threats in the protection of public spaces, also inherently integrating security-by-design concepts.

2. SVA Development process

The SVA framework (Fig. 1) was developed within the SAFE-CITIES project following an iterative process where project partners interacted between them in order to:

1. understand the needs and requirements of public space protection frameworks,
2. capture the operational experiences of the LEAs, emergency responders, municipalities and other authorities through targeted interactions,
3. synthesize existing frameworks from the literature and operational experiences.

The SVA framework was then assembled into a 12-step process that is analytically presented in the next section. It was refined based on the following specific requirements and needs, addressing key challenges in the security domain shown in Table 1.

Table 1. SVA key principles

Single solution to account for all phases of security and emergency response actions
Consistency across normal conditions within urban environments and also mass gatherings / events
Multi-stakeholder partnerships, across the public and private sector
Citizen Engagement through local community networks
Support the “Security-by-design”, through the Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design (CPTED) concept
Seamlessly introduce conventional and also emerging threats such as UAS
SVA has a static and dynamic component
Vulnerability considers operational, technological and human aspects

The SVA process was reviewed in a dedicated workshop that was conducted in the city of Gdansk (Poland) with the participation of the SAFE-CITIES partners and external stakeholders. The participants’ comments were subsequently integrated in the final version of the introduced framework.

3. The SAFE-CITIES Security and Vulnerability Framework

This section introduces the SVA steps as finally derived from the iterative process identified previously (Fig 1.)

Figure 1. SVA Process diagram

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3.1 Step 1. Identify the SVA Team

129

Each public space SVA project is unique and will require the establishment of an integrated team with expertise that matches the goals of the project. However, an effective SVA requires a highly trained team with extensive knowledge and experience in the design and assessment of protection systems. Table 2 below presents an indicate descriptive analysis of roles and responsibilities that can be followed by those organizations (e.g., local municipalities / event managers) that will assign internally or procure the conduction of an SVA.

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Table 2. SVA Team roles and responsibilities

137

Roles	Responsibilities
Project Manager (or managing team)	Selects administrative and security professionals with sufficient expertise. Sets realistic schedules and budgets (when appropriate). Understands the opportunities and orchestrates the team to achieve a holistic vision. Leads the team to innovative and successful solutions.
Public Space (or) Event Managers	Support a long-term development strategy and comprehensive site design. Support long-term management and maintenance. Advocate realistic and innovative solutions that serve the public space and the municipality. Share expertise on the detailed operation and everyday functionality of the building and site. Establish relationships with stakeholders.
Municipalities / Local Authorities	Budget planning and scheduling Provide advice and best practices. Support multifaceted, holistic strategies linked to local/national policies. Identify acceptable risk levels
Security Experts	Demonstrated understanding and expertise in risk management. Knowledge in physical protection and also countermeasures. Ability to include balanced cost and risk mitigation measures.

Communities and Stakeholders NGO, Special interest groups (commercial, hotels, events, education)	Continuous involvement Introduce local knowledge, culture, social perspectives and related programs. Leverage and identify local resources that could be mobilized Provide information on potential risks, acceptable risks levels and possible/practical mitigation. Plan effective risk communication
Security Professionals LEA, First / Secondary responders, Private security, Security consultants	Assess vulnerabilities and prioritize countermeasures. Provide physical protection recommendations (including organizational and procedures elements) Support development of multifaceted tools and solutions. Seek and implement creative and flexible countermeasures. Propose training curricula / possible existing courses Plan different types of exercises
Designers and Planners (Architect, Landscape Architect, Planner, Urban Designer), Engineers (Civil, Structural, Geotechnical, Environmental), IT experts	Work within a long-term development strategy. Develop a strategic, multidimensional, and holistic site design. Work closely with security professionals to create flexible alternatives and innovative solutions. Support collaborative teamwork early in analysis.
Media / Communication Team	Generates communication material – potentially oriented towards special groups / local areas Promotes security policies Informs public in case of security incident / increased threat level

3.2 Step 2. Plan the SVA.

The next phase includes the development of a project plan outlining how the SVA will be conducted and key assumptions made. The project lead will build on the 1st phase with respect to the identification of team members’ roles and responsibilities, developing the SVA schedule, gathering and distributing preliminary data and information to prepare for the public space characterization survey.

The SVA needs to be aligned with local socio-institutional and cultural dimensions, as defined / communicated by potential stakeholders. It also needs to consider important aspects such as: a) public space characteristics such as cultural importance and role in community, b) demographics and societal characteristics of the public on the site, c) constraints and requirements from the various stakeholders, d) budget, e) security threats / risks, f) solutions for risk mitigation and their public acceptance, etc. Furthermore, particular characteristics and functions of the different stakeholders, and their operational framework should be also considered that includes national / regional / local procedures and practices, national and local legislation and security culture. Other elements could be related to the organizational dimensions such as interoperability across organizational, procedural, operational and institutional roles boundaries. Some indicative issues that could be considered include initiation of interaction and discussion between stakeholders, exchanging information channels and technologies, best practices and shared understanding, common level of awareness concerning the SVA of a public space and the finalization of a common approach.

Within the *SVA planning phase it is extremely important to define the accepted levels of risk (or tolerable risk), which* will guide several decisions needed to implement the SVA assessment and risk prioritization activities. Another important point that needs to be discussed and acknowledged is that not all threats can be prevented, but identify those that can be mitigated, within budgetary constraints and societal perceptions, thus deciding what threats / vulnerabilities / risk levels are accepted as not being possible to prevent,

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or would require excessive measures (in terms of costs, personnel and capabilities and what mitigating measures to put in place). This process could entail physical protection systems and their performance metrics and other key performance indicators (and also could include their accepted target values).

When relevant, *SVA should include cross-border cooperation and coordination* in both enhancing the capacity of law enforcement and identifying good practices that could be introduced, such as security measures taken during major sports events, in public transport facilities, in public areas of international airports and at tourist sites.

3.3 Step 3. Define the Threat vector

A vital part of the SVA is to establish an understanding about the threat vectors that could act as adversaries potentially defeating the public space security provisions, also detailing to the widest possible degree their capabilities and characteristics. This process is critical for:

- Understanding the threats that the public space is exposed to.
- Conducting an accurate SVA and plan for security upgrades.
- Prioritize between short-term security upgrades (ad-hoc actions) and also long-term investments.

Owing to the rapid, dynamic evolution in the adversary tactics require a continuous analysis of the potential threats, including emerging threats due to technological advances (e.g. unmanned systems) and also assessment of their intentions. Within the proposed SVA the following set of threat assessment can be considered.

3.3.1 Identification of threats

The list of threats could be wide, and thus continuously updated by the responsible security experts (LEA, private or consultants) considering both local threat environment and a global assessment. The following Table 3 introduces a provisional list of threats from the EU VAT [4], where both the University of Maryland Global Threat Database¹, and the IAEA Design Basis Threat [14] have been taken into account.

Table 3. Baseline list of public space threats

Type of Attack	
Unauthorized entry	Access to protected / closed areas by non-authorized persons
Civil Disturbance	Disruption of community function that requires intervention
Vandalism	Acts of destruction of public space objects
Unauthorised removal of valuables	Theft / Robbery
Fire arms attack	Small pistols or automatic rifles
Sharp object attack	Sharp and blunt objects (e.g., knives)
Vehicle Attack	Vehicle as a weapon e.g. ramming large crowds
IED	Any type of explosives in objects or goods
PBIED	Explosives concealed on a person (e.g., suicide)
RC/UAS - IED	Remote controlled or UAS delivered explosive device
VBIED	Vehicle born explosive devices
Chemical attack	Toxic or harmful chemical in goods or carried items
Biological attack	Deliberately released biological pathogen
Radiological attack	Deliberately released radioactive material as is (RED - exposure device) or combined with dispersal material (RDD – dispersal device)

3.3.2 Characterization and ranking of adversaries

¹ <https://www.start.umd.edu/gtd/>

Under the proposed SVA approach, the adversaries could be characterised following the intent and capability approach (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Threat characterization

Intent can be further analysed into two components: (i) the desire to realize the threat (e.g., including Likely attitude to radiological and other risks to themselves) and (ii) the motivation to pursue an appropriate course of action towards realizing the threat. **Capabilities** to carry out the threat effectively, also further analysed into: (i) resources (human, material, technical, logistics, financial etc.) needed for execution of a threat plan and (ii) collected knowledge (facility, attacking, planning, logistics) required to mobilize resources and to inform the plan with vulnerability data to carry out the threat effectively. This approach facilitates the quantification of the threat likelihood. The likelihood can be further elaborated using historical data on the public space of interest, and the crime statistics of the city / country / region of interest. A potential categorization can be found in Table 4.

Table 4. Baseline list of public space threats

Category	Intent		Capabilities	
	Motivation	Desire	Resources (material, funding)	Knowledge (Training)
Very Low	No expectation to succeed	Little or no desire	Few , if any	None
Low	Limited capacity to succeed	Use peaceful means	Limited	limited
Medium	Reasonable expectation to succeed	Flexibility for methods used	Moderate	Moderate
High	High expectation to succeed	Limited room to compromise decisions , tend for extreme actions	Significant	Skills and training
Very High	Sure to succeed	No room for compromise, potential suicide	Fully	Military / SOF training

3.3.3 Design Basis / Reference Threat

In parallel to the identified and categorised assessment of the potential adversaries, it is useful to determine a set of attributes establishing the profile of the type, composition, and capabilities of adversaries. It is an estimate of the threat across a range of undesirable events and is usually based on the best available information, reports, assessments, and crime statistics at the time of the SVA. Linking it with the threat assessment, the following parameters could be used [14] to characterize the adversary group: a) Number of attackers, b) presence of active and/or passive Insider, c) Willing to Kill/Die, d) type of weapons

/ firearms, e) use of explosives, f) tools and equipment, g) transportation, h) other technical skills (e.g. cyber, UAS), i) use of deception and/or diversion and j) planning of attack

3.3.4 Emerging Threat landscape – Unmanned Systems

Use of commercial UAS's is growing rapidly. Technology is getting better and prices are descending, making them affordable for more people. Along with benefits the drones also produce different mild effects. After several years of active consideration to drones from security and safety perspective of LEA, we can see that the unmanned systems are causing opportunities but at the same time new kind of threats in society for public and private properties. The nature of public space and protectable interest increases the complexity for countering UAS (CUAS). Locating the UAS is challenging because of the reflections caused by buildings whereas the use of kinetic counter measures (firearm, net gun, laser) is not risk free because of crowds and inhabitants. Advanced autonomous systems opt out human error but might make the procedure considered unethical. Human-in-the-loop is still often considered mandatory.

The starting point from the public safety perspective is that legislation and advanced guidance will reduce unnecessary countermeasures. New threats need continuous planning from public safety perspective and architectural planning will offer new solutions against the threats. For example, the international community has witnessed how UAS have a crucial role in Ukraine, without state borders being an obstacle.

3.4 Step 4. Characterization of the public space

This process involves the assessment, identification and characterization of the public space in urban context including societal, urban planning, design issues, and the physical condition of the public space. All information and data collected will be used to fully understand what must be protected (targets – step 5), from whom (threats – step 3), and to what performance level (step 6).

Public space has been defined as an environment where people meet, and the relationships entailed by people's interactions (whether intentional or not) take shape. They are spaces for protest, participation, performance, self-expression, relaxation, activity, reflection, which can be used alone or in groups, indoors or outdoors, central to urban life and to the creation of a plural public sphere. Although the typology of public spaces is potentially innumerable, examples include tourist sites, transport hubs, shopping malls, places of worship, outdoor markets, concert halls and city squares [1], but also parks, streets, pedestrian areas, sporting events or festivals.

The characteristics of the public spaces should also be part of this assessment process: public spaces can be categorized as "open", "semi-open" or "closed", characterized by a high concentration of people and access properties, combined with inadequate or complete lack of security measures depending on the case (e.g., closed privately owned vs open public owned areas). Unlike privately owned buildings/areas with restricted access, the open and uncontrolled access may result to looser security measures in an effort to avoid interference with a site functionality and aesthetics, in order to avoid legislation and ethical issues, or to avoid causing a sense of fear and insecurity to the public. However, the lack of security measures may render a public site vulnerable to manmade threats such as potential terrorist attacks or regular criminal activity. Identifying security gaps through systemic analysis can support informed risk decisions, so that smart security measures are taken in harmony with the safety, functional requirements and type of a specific public space of interest.

SAFE-CITIES builds up on the awareness that protection and accessibility/ openness might contrast with each other, if they are not designed and developed properly; therefore, the project aims to adopt a 'security-by-design' approach, a term used to describe "urban design integrating security measures into public spaces and streets without

compromising the functions or aesthetics of the space” [3]. Security-by-design is based on four main key principles describing such an intent:

- **proportionality**: adequate and balanced security measures with respect to the risk to be faced in order to reduce the impact on daily social and economic activities;
- **multi-functionality**: safety principles considered (and applied) right from the early stages of design or redesign process, leading to integrated, multifunctional and high aesthetic quality solutions, containing construction costs;
- **stakeholder cooperation**: holistic cooperation among different stakeholders involved (authorities, architects, planners and police, security specialists, civil society, etc.) is a necessary condition for quality public spaces equipped with effective and properly designed security solutions;
- **design aesthetics**: solutions embedded into the morphology/design of public spaces capable of combining aesthetics, comfort, usability and functionality in terms of safety without being intrusive or inducing anxiety/fear in civil society.

3.4.1 Security-by-design

The security-by-design approach frames into the ‘environmental’ prevention line traced by the ‘CPTED-Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design’ [15] multi-disciplinary methodology focusing on urban and architectural design, management of built and natural environments. The CPTED acts on all the physical elements present in a certain context to prevent a criminal event from happening, following six main concepts/strategies: territoriality (enhance the sense of appropriation to a specific site); natural surveillance (maximized visibility, social control and interactions); access control (well defined entrance-exit spaces/points); well maintenance and management; activity support (promote functions generating safety perception, e.g., playgrounds); and target hardening (defence of possible specific crime targets). Concepts - largely based on the crucial role of community participation in prevention measures - that can be implemented adopting specific solutions and design strategies (e.g., display security system signage at access points, include public transport, pedestrian and cycle routes, install closed-circuit cameras, schedule activities, place amenities in common areas in order to attract a larger number of users, promote neighbourhoods with mixed population targets, follow specific urban lighting design principles, define behavioural rules for targeted spaces, use adequate materials and installation rules for furniture, etc.).

Interventions on public spaces embedding safety principles and goals into the design choices should be intended as complementary to other more traditional approaches to urban security, based respectively on the maintenance of public order through the law and the presence of law enforcement; and on interventions at social level, aiming at the reduction of conditions of disadvantage and deprivation, considered as a factor increasing the risk of criminal acts. In this framework, counter-terrorist safety and security measures should consider and be tailored made to the peculiar feature and nature of public spaces to be protected/under risk and, therefore, incorporate a combination of approaches, strategies and measures, (if applicable) from the very onset of the planning and design process in order to be better integrated within the surrounding built or natural environment (Table 5).

Table 5. Summary of urban design principles for safe public spaces (source: SAFE CITIES project)

Avoid an oversensitivity to risk (and, consequently, ensure a proportionality between measures and potential risks), ensuring a balance between safety/protection and open nature of public are-as/openness
Integrate safety into the planning and design processes, based on shared informed decisions following more collaborative and inclusive processes among as wider as possible stakeholder groups

Combine the creation of a barriers or boundaries protection systems with a physical design of the space and integrate additional protection according to the existing layout/asset able to prevent risks and threats and in order to respect and complain with its function, social and symbolic value
Consider security measures from the early stage of design process in order to complain with an integrated vision of 'beautiful, sustainable and inclusive' public spaces, in line with the New European Bauhaus principles
Consider the adoption of standardized urban furniture (e.g., benches, bollards, rails and fences, and natural barriers) as well as ad-hoc protective measures (e.g., public art), promoting multifunctionality and ensuring a balance
Consider the presence of physical measures in the streetscape for specific attacks, combining general planning principles, attention to access points and boundaries, identify sensitive points, identify targeted routes and access points
Concentrating vehicle flows with specific systems to be integrated into the public space providing/defining obstacles and surveillance measures
Design climate and environmental mitigations solution (e.g., plants, water retention devices, etc.) in a multifunctional way to serve as a protective measure

3.4.2 Categories of Public Spaces of relevance to SAFE-CITIES

Public spaces are closely linked to the people’s leisure and quality of living and may carry economic, commercial, cultural, historic, religious, archaeological value or constitute a point of geographical reference with high concentration of people. These may include closed or open areas such as transport hubs, open squares, parks, shopping areas, nightlife areas, cultural venues, business venues, places of worship, or institutional venues/buildings. Technically, some public spaces are semi-public spaces and are privately-owned or privately-operated spaces (e.g., train/ metro stations, shopping malls). The categorization on Table 6 is based upon [1]

Table 6. Public Space Categorization (list in alphabetic order)

Type of Public Space	
Business	Hotels, large office spaces, conferences
Cultural	Concert hall, museum, monuments, sport events, stadiums, amusement parks, tourist sites, etc
Institutional spaces	Public buildings, healthcare buildings, education buildings,
Nightlife areas	High density of bars, pubs and/or nightclubs, restaurants, coffee shops, small concert halls
Religion / Worship	Churches, mosques, etc
Shopping areas	Malls, main shopping streets in city centres
Squares	Squares were many events take place, next to important buildings, have regular big markets, festivals, etcetera.
Transport hubs	Train station, bus hub, underground metro stations, airports, etc.

3.5 Step 5. Identify the Targets and quantify their attractiveness.

Target analysis involves the identification and characterization of the importance of public spaces that must be protected to ensure a high level of security system effectiveness against defined threats. Target attractiveness can be quantified using commonly obtained parameters and serves as an effective means of ranking different and diverse areas against a common system.

Different metrics domains can be used, and categorization can be by defining a number of scales (e.g. three or five), Table 7, effectively trying to provide an objective and coherent response to the question “Why preferring one target as opposed to another?”. The relative ranking of the criteria can be performed based on commonly agreed weighting factors, but this is important to maintain constant through-out a city-wide assessment.

Table 7. Public space attractiveness factors

343

Factor	Explanation
Accessibility / Escape	How easily an adversary can access to / escape from a public space
Existing protection	How protected is a site based on its existing security measures against man-made threats
Iconic Value / Symbolism	If the public space is itself or has proximity to national landmarks and global heritage sites (e.g. UNESCO), and has symbolic / economic / cultural / religious importance
Potentially Exposed Citizens	Number of people on a daily basis or for specific events (in absolute numbers, relative and crowd density)
Criticality	If the public space has many critical areas for the functioning of the city, area such as public /private infrastructures etc.
Media	Media exposure of the attack
Impacts	Potentially maximise impacts including societal disruption (Linked to Step 7)

3.6 Step 6. Describe the public space security system

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A detailed security system characterization includes identifying public space security elements that provide detection, assessment, delay, and response capabilities. A thorough on-site survey allows security specialists to identify all protection elements and collect performance data for each component and the system as a whole. Presently physical protection and security systems of public spaces have four core functionalities that include:

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Figure 3. Overview of Public Space physical security regime

The security system establishment should be linked to a long-term development strategy and a comprehensive design that is based on sufficient funding and continuous monitoring through-out the life span of the project. The team should integrate all aspects of the security requirements into the overall project requirements and design directives. Understanding all components that contribute to the security of a public space is necessary to establish priorities and phased implementation if this becomes necessary. Innovative design concepts should have the flexibility to respond to future changes public space, stakeholders' roles and national regulatory changes, operations, or budgets. Over the next paragraphs we introduce some security concepts that can be implemented by the public space stakeholders during the SVA implementation

3.6.1 Community Policing

Community policing is a strategy of policing that focuses on building ties and working closely with members of the community through interactions with local agencies and members of the public, creating partnerships and strategies for reducing crime and disorder. The concept is traditionally used by local LEAs that have a direct impact on everyday security of a community and affect citizen quality of life. This approach is commonly used as a form of gathering intelligence. The interaction between the police and the public can provide an important source of information and therefore guide the actions of the LEAs. Through the effective implementation of this concept citizens can become key players and reliable partners to "co-produced" security.

3.6.2 Physical Protection Systems design considerations

Since many physical security systems have a longer usable life than initial planning assumptions, design solutions, there is the need to establish multifunctional and agile provisions that are able to serve the facility efficiently over time, as needs change. Best practices for public space security design includes the selection of elements that support security functions in multiple ways, by providing the following:

- Physical deterrence, e.g. elements expanding the buffer zones and use physical barriers to keep vehicles from driving into the area or installation through entrances or the like, or through spaces below ground.
- Psychological deterrence, having the ability to design very obvious and almost forbidding security measures, and the presence of alert and trained personnel may be enough for a perpetrator to refrain from an attack.
- Establish access restrictions and consider to access control and security checks when appropriate
- Support for observation, surveillance, and inspection. Allow sight lines and vistas that provide natural opportunities for observation of those approaching the public space, or to block views of sensitive areas. Camera surveillance and monitoring by security personnel can deter a perpetrator or expose preparations.
- Protective measures against explosives, which is usually is to increase the distance between what is to be protected and the presumed attack site. Another measure may be to reduce the effect of fragments from glass in (surrounding) buildings, or enforce sufficient resistance to explosions.

3.7 Step 7. Conduct risk assessment

A key outcome of the SVA is the risk assessment and risk quantification of threats for public spaces and urban environments of interest. A semi-empirical, scenario (threat) based specific assessment can be implemented that require to determine the likelihood of a successful action of the said adversary and the potential impacts, multi-dimensional

nature. The former can be directly linked to the characterization of the threat (step 3) and for the later the following factors are recommended (Table 8)

Table 8. Public Space Impact factors

Factor	Explanation
Exposed People - Crowd density	Number of people potentially exposed in the attack per square meter unit – not necessarily casualties or otherwise injured
Exposed buildings	Number of buildings exposed to the attack (and also those potentially damaged)
Potential Economic Loses	Potential economic losses quantified in some currency
Critical services	Number of critical services (utilities, societal, government) that could stop functioning
Environmental damages	Impacts to the environment and ecosystems (also consider NATURA and other protected areas)
Reputation	Impact on the reputation of the attacked region (feeling of in-security to the citizens)
Societal impacts	Disruption to societal functioning, changes in security perceptions
Political impacts	New legislations, changes of organizational processes, political views

Once the levels of the severity and likelihood of a successful threat scenario have been assessed, through a categorical scale, the risk level of each scenario can be determined with the help of a risk matrix which quantifies the level of risk and provides a link to the acceptability of each security risk and a relative ranking between different risk and public spaces in the region. Examples (Table 9) include a risk matrix, with three levels of risk.

Table 9. Example 5x5 Risk matrix

		IMPACTS				
		VERY LOW	LOW	MED	HIGH	VERY HIGH
LIKELIHOOD	VERY HIGH					
	HIGH					
	MED					
	LOW					
	VERYLOW					
RISK LEGEND						

Within this table, and based on the perceived risk levels (Step 2), non-acceptable level of risks can be defined which is an indication for further improvement in countermeasures (risks assigned an orange/ red colour); an acceptable level of risk (assigned a blue/green colour) where it is considered that sufficient countermeasures have been implemented for the assessed threat scenario.

3.8 Step 8. Scenario Building: Determine the most vulnerable path and develop worse-case scenarios

The site data collected, and assumptions reached in order to implement Step 4 and Step 6 are used to construct credible dynamic adversary “attack pathways” to the selected targets areas. Different types of assessments that could include: a) expert analysis, e.g.,

narratives and short stories, based on site surveys, b) table-top exercises, and c) advanced computer models could be used to construct adversary pathways including the security elements and provisions of the public space. Using site collected data it is possible to quantify each path, and the results to be used for the determination of the most vulnerable and accessible paths and potential attackers' detection points.

Although different risk scenarios could be used for this assessment, the majority of the analysis is recommended for "worst-case and/or high-risk scenarios". These can be developed by combining the most impactful risk, pertaining to the most vulnerable paths with the public space security system perceived response to an attack. Within this assessment it is possible to identify detection probabilities (by both human and surveillance systems) and path delays. The identified pathways and attackers/responders movements should be thoroughly reviewed to avoid "super-human" actions, to validate the scenario credibility and reflect real-world conditions, using performance-based data. All potential and credible attack options should be studied to ensure that worse-case attacks and other serious options that need to be protected against are identified.

For the analysis, attack scenarios are described step-by-step, including when the adversary is detected, all adversary task times, and when the response force assesses and communicates the intrusion and interrupts the adversary's actions. These scenarios are used to estimate probability of neutralization.

3.9 Step 9. Attack Neutralization and Analysis

This analysis provides information about how effective the response force will be at neutralizing the threat using the identified scenarios of the previous step. The assessment should evaluate the physical protection measures and organizational establishment, including the timely response of the security (public and private) personnel and LEA response forces. This assessment can be conducted using:

- Empirical methods based on data, such as adversary numbers, capabilities, and equipment and response / security personnel numbers, capabilities, and equipment.
- Data intense empirical methods, considering initial locations, path and locations of security/response force and the adversaries, terrain/buildings, PPS characteristics.
- Full-Scale and Table-Top Exercises could be used to simulate the interruption and neutralization of threat actions.
- Probabilistic models for assessing the neutralization probabilities for different combinations of security personnel and adversaries.

3.10 Step 10. Identify and Quantify vulnerabilities, determine areas for improvement, and propose upgrades

Once the previous steps have been completed, the SVA process will summarize all vulnerable points (both from the static assessment – step 6 and the dynamic process – steps 8 and 9) to perform an in-depth Vulnerability Assessment of the public space. This covers the baseline current situation and decides on the effectiveness of the security elements in protecting public spaces against the identified threat. If overall public space security meets determined requirements on accepted risk (step 2), then the assessment is complete. Otherwise, areas for improvement are proposed.

The process of identifying vulnerabilities encompasses a thorough security survey, assessing exploitable situations resulting from inadequate security measures, personal behaviour, construction techniques, or insufficient security procedures. Assessing of weak / vulnerable elements of the public space can include the following elements:

Structural and design issues where examples include: a) poor perimeter fencing with holes, gaps, etc., b) building design that inhibit access control measures, ground floor windows, etc., c) tunnels and drains that permit approach by an adversary, d) unsecured doors, e) parking lots provide adversaries with a venue for observing a facility, perpetrating a crime, detonating mobile explosive devices, etc. f) vehicle barriers that are not and

appropriate, g) untrained guard forces and h) insufficient access control that allows adversaries a potential means of entry either detected or undetected and many more.

Technical, operational and support equipment, that allows for a) signal interceptions that can occur when using devices like cell phones, wireless networked computers, b) unauthorized control of telecommunications and information systems equipment, c) equipment tampering and d) remote activation/operation permitting an adversary to remotely activate and/or operate equipment.

Organizational / Decision making process that could be linked to a) poor practices, e.g. failure to develop and operate a property control system, b) observable practices and activities, c) Operations Security deficiencies etc.

Human factors & security culture that may include a) insider threats, b) anger management problems, c) ignorance of technology, d) behavioural issues for disgruntled personnel, persons with personality disorders, etc. e) greed, persons who are greedy may compromise or steal critical assets for personal gain, f) Bored/Tired Persons that may become careless etc.

The SVA team should review the baseline system effectiveness and proceed with a determination of the effectiveness of the security system elements in protecting targets against the examined threat. If overall system effectiveness or VA meets the determined requirements (as defined in step 2), then the assessment is complete. A potential high level VA indicator category is proposed within Table 10.

Otherwise, system vulnerabilities are identified and areas for improvement are proposed. Both improvements to the PPS functions (detection, delay, and response) and to the overall system should be considered for increasing the system effectiveness.

The following sections describe an initial set of indicators that can be used to provide quantifiable metrics and support the SVA process. The project team can select the most pertinent indicators and provide informed categorization based on historical data, expert opinions and literature review.

Table 10. VA Indicator categories

Indicator	Explanation
Human factors	Composition of participants, important people, organizers, event management personnel ability
Management and prevention factors	Guarantee for the security operation of public space including the relevant schemes and technical means, SVA assessments
Site and equipment factors	Site / equipment condition, daily management and maintenance of the equipment, and the equipment usage optimization.
Risk factors	Domestic and foreign political situation, type and nature of event, social situation and attention of event
PPS effectiveness	Probability of interruption of attack * probability of neutralization of the adversary
Security factors	Security of public space, Behaviour score on security classification for access control, response measures (permanent and ad hoc)
Building factors	Ownership and importance, clustering and proximity to iconic / symbolic buildings
Policy factors	Level of cross- and within institutional coordination, dominant policy, budgetary issues
Response factors	Countermeasures tested, incident response time, communication chain and effectiveness

3.11 Step 11. Re-evaluate public space with Proposed Improvements

If the SVA from the previous step was not assessed as final, then the process should be conducted again, taking into account the proposed and postulated upgrades. Once the

upgrades are planned and/or defined, a new VA should be conducted and related metrics should be determined, provided that all assumptions made are kept constant. The process is repeated until upgrades are satisfactory addressing the system vulnerabilities and are increasing the overall public space's security in an effective manner. Societal and urban planning component of the public space should also be considered (step 4).

A risk-informed, risk reduction approach should be followed, (step 7), prioritizing the interventions on assets that are exposed to the highest risk levels supported by a cost-benefit analysis, resulting in a trade-off. Innovative elements of public space protection such as enhanced public – private cooperation, local citizens networks and advanced simulation capabilities should be considered

3.12 Step 12. Report Results and Recommendations

The final step of the SVA is reporting the results in a manner usable to the responsible decision-makers. The goal of the reporting phase is to provide accurate unbiased information that clearly and in detail defines the current security effectiveness and provides potential solutions in case of system's ineffectiveness.

4. SVA testing and evaluation protocol

Any SVA framework should be linked with suitable testing and evaluation in order to a) assess their correctness and robustness, b) improve the data collection process for future SVA and c) develop, and update emergency response and security upgrade action plans, programs, policies and procedures. The following types could be considered:

Multidisciplinary workshops with the participation of related stakeholders, responsible for the protection of public spaces. The workshops provide a good opportunity for the generation of ideas, information sharing, exchange of good practices and raising the stakeholder's risk awareness. Moreover, the interaction can contribute towards a common language and common risk understanding and communication.

Discussion-based exercise, which requires little resources and can be handled internally and does not disrupt or interrupt the public space daily routine.

Field exercises that require major resources and more planning (also involve external actors). However, they can identify problems in security measures implemented. All employees have the opportunity to practice their roles, but can create confidence that real events or incidents can be handled.

Public Space Tabletop Exercises should be designed and implemented to assist the stakeholders by leveraging on existing knowledge and SVA results and be flexibly tailored to their specific needs. A main recommendation of the public space community would be to prepare templates and examples.

The developed SVA will be initially tested in all pilot sites against multiple threat scenarios to (a) demonstrate its validity and acceptance by the project's stakeholders, (b) collect reference data in support of the further development and elaboration of the SVA

4.1 SVA methodology validation

Security practitioners, responsible for the protection of public spaces, have been gathered in face-to-face workshop, organised by Polish Platform for Homeland Security, in Gdansk (May 2023) in order to use and test proposed SVA methodology on pre-defined security scenarios: 1) Clashes/fights between fans several hours before the game at the Railway Station; 2) Clashes/fights between fans immediately after the football game started at the stadium in Gdansk; 3) Mass shooting terrorist attack during the Christmas shopping period; 4) CBRN attack during a high-intensity shopping day; 5) Suicide terrorist attack after the headliner concert; 6) Bombing attack using drones; 7) False bomb alert in a crowded square, and 8) Car driving into the crowd. The main objectives of the proposed tabletop exercises are:

- To apply the methodology to selected security scenarios;

- To define if the proposed methodology would have allowed security practitioners to prevent/anticipate the security incident defined? And how the risk would have been mitigated; 575
- To evaluate is the methodology: Comprehensive? Simple or Complex? Applicable to real-life situations; 576
- To identify the strengths and weakness of the proposed methodology; 577
- To propose practical improvements and/or define the areas for improvements. 578

Several groups have been formed, composed of different expertise and background in order to stimulate knowledge exchange and constructive discussions, and invited to apply the SVA methodology on two security scenarios. Several iterations took place, and group leaders shared and argued findings and recommendations with other groups. Finally, all feedback and recommendations have been collected for further processing and implementation; thus, contributing to the fine-tuning and enhancement of the SVA methodology. 579

5. SVA data requirements 588

This section provides a description of the necessary data to be collected covering different databases and scope (urban configuration, threat vectors, risk assessment, etc). During the creation of the environment a baseline geo-referenced map (GIS), should be used to precisely locate the position of the venue, assets and people within the environment, also introducing a BIM model of the public space where the team wants to conduct the SVA representing the environment, including urban furniture or security systems, like lampposts or CCTVs. Before executing the simulation of scenarios, different types of data and information are needed, which can be organized in three main steps: (a) the definition of the event(s), (b) the definition of potential threats and impacts, (c) the definition of the parameters to setup the Risk Assessment process. 589

In order to create an SVA threat scenario, the user shall first define the type of event to be investigated (e.g. music show, Christmas market, etc.). Moreover, the user will have to provide some information about the crowd behaviour and pattern, which will be different, based on the specific type of event: this will define suitable threat/impact parameters like crowd profile, traffic flows, define which security measures, personnel and procedures are in place, as this will enable testing how different procedures and counter-measures can influence the vulnerabilities and the impact of attacks. 590

Another fundamental aspect in order to be able to conduct the simulation is the definition of threats and impacts. The user will have to define the types of attacks to be simulated and, for each of them, some kind of plot: information like time evolution of the attacks, the magnitude and impacts of the attack, based both on historical data and user's experience on the matter and the local environment. All this information will be key for a realistic simulation of the attack scenarios. 591

In order to be able to perform a risk assessment capable of providing realistic and valuable insights, the user shall also specify, for each asset and security measure in the site, their CAPEX (Capital Expenditure) and OPEX (Operational Expenditure). This will allow the user to conduct a cost-benefit analysis and support her/him in the identification of which security measures and procedures are the most cost-efficient, as well as which scenarios are the riskiest ones in financial terms. In order to provide a more comprehensive assessment, additional information shall be provided by the user, related to the attractiveness of the site based on its role in the city, the citizens' perception and social acceptance of security measures, and any socially relevant information, like parameters related to accessibility or security-by-design. 592

6. Conclusions 622

The protection of public spaces is of major concern within cities and municipalities, balancing between citizen's rights, accessibility whilst at the same time enjoying safety and security. At the same time, these places are potentially soft attractive targets and highly 623

exposed to diverse security threats. The present work introduces a holistic Security and Vulnerability Assessment framework that is developed within the SAFE-CITIES European research funded project that can provide risk-informed support to the place-making approach. It aspires to close existing gaps in related activities by proposing a 12-step SVA process, that is fully compatible with international standards and builds on existing EU related initiatives (such as the PRoTECT, EU VAT).

The present work, developed through the framework of the Horizon Europe SAFE-CITIES funded project defines a systematic Security and Vulnerability Assessment (SVA) for public spaces that is based on formal risk management (e.g., ISO31000) and the EU Vulnerability Assessment practices [4], previous and ongoing research results and actions, characterizing the security functions of a public space, including its physical protection and emergency response after major events. Through the facilitation of multi-stakeholders' partnerships and citizen engagement, the proposed framework has the inherent capability to consider security-by-design of public spaces and also drive risk-informed interventions for the protection of public urban spaces and mass events and support optimal allocation of resources. It is also an inherent approach that allows to tackle different adversarial threats that include CBRN (e.g., RDD, RED) and the use of emerging technologies such as UAS.

Supplementary Materials: NOT AVAILABLE.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, A.S.; methodology, A.S, G.K., I.T.; writing—original draft preparation, ALL; writing—review and editing, A.S.; project administration, U.B.; All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research was funded by European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101073945 (SAFE-CITIES)

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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7. The project was funded by the European Union's Internal Security Fund – Police (<https://www.stepwise-project.eu>)
8. European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 883286
9. European Union's H2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 883522
10. The project was funded under Societal Challenges - Smart, Green And Integrated Transport
11. The project was funded by the European Union's Internal Security Fund- Police (<https://www.pactesur.eu/>)
12. Co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund through the Urban Innovative Actions Initiative under grant agreement number UIA04-274.
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